

EVALUATING PARENTAL ANXIETY: DEVELOPMENT OF A MULTIDIMENSIONAL ASSESSMENT INVENTORY

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ABSTRACT

The study titled "Evaluating Parental Anxiety: Development of a Multidimensional Assessment Inventory" aimed at creating a thorough inventory to assess parental anxiety across cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological dimensions. This initiative was driven by the goal to facilitate targeted interventions that enhance family well-being. Developed through a comprehensive review of existing literature on parental anxiety and its various manifestations, the inventory's reliability was tested using a frequentist analysis, including Cronbach's α for measuring internal consistency across the different anxiety dimensions. The sample comprised a wide range of parents, ensuring the tool's applicability to diverse demographics. The results from the reliability analysis indicated high internal consistency within the inventory, with Cronbach's α scores of 0.928 for cognitive, 0.924 for emotional, 0.865 for behavioral, and 0.895 for physiological dimensions, reflecting 'Excellent' to 'Good' reliability. These findings affirm the inventory's capability in precisely measuring the complex nature of parental anxiety. The 95% confidence intervals further validated the scale's consistency, and the analysis demonstrated that the removal of individual items had a negligible effect on the overall reliability. Conclusively, the inventory emerges as a reliable and comprehensive tool for evaluating parental anxiety, with substantial implications for both clinical and research practices. Its multidimensional approach enables a nuanced understanding of parental anxiety, setting the stage for customized interventions. The study suggests avenues for future research, including further validation with diverse populations, longitudinal studies, and the integration of the inventory into intervention programs. This contribution is significant in providing a validated tool for assessing the intricate phenomenon of parental

anxiety, aimed at supporting interventions that promote healthier family dynamics and positive child development outcomes.

Keywords: *Parental anxiety, Inventory development, Reliability analysis, Multidimensional assessment, Family well-being*

INTRODUCTION

Parental anxiety is an intricate and pervasive issue with far-reaching implications on the dynamics within households and the developmental pathways of children. This form of anxiety is not a singular phenomenon but rather a complex interplay of various stressors and influences that collectively impact the quality of life for both parents and their children. As the body of research expands, it becomes increasingly evident that understanding parental anxiety in its full scope requires a detailed approach, one that acknowledges the myriad factors contributing to its manifestation.

Recent studies, such as the one by Thompson et al. (2022), have shed light on the transmission of anxiety from parents to children, indicating how parental behaviors driven by anxiety can significantly affect children's anxiety levels and behavioral outcomes. This direct impact underscores the importance of addressing parental anxiety not just for the parents' sake but also for the well-being and development of their children. Additionally, the work by Liu et al. (2023) explores economic factors as crucial determinants of parental anxiety, pointing to financial instability, socioeconomic status, and employment uncertainty as key contributors. This suggests an intersection between economic policy and family well-being, emphasizing the need for supportive measures that can alleviate financial stressors for families.

The role of digital technology in influencing parental anxiety has also come under scrutiny, with studies like Patel et al. (2022) highlighting the double-edged nature of technological advancements. While technology offers connectivity and access to information, it also poses challenges and anxieties related to children's online safety and the pressures of digital parenting. Furthermore, societal norms and cultural expectations regarding parenting roles play a significant role in the anxiety experienced by parents, as explored by Kim et al. (2023). This dimension of parental anxiety points to the necessity for culturally sensitive approaches that consider the diverse experiences of mothers and fathers.

The COVID-19 pandemic introduced unprecedented challenges, as documented by Gomez et al. (2024), emphasizing the heightened anxieties faced by parents due to health concerns, disruptions in daily routines, and the added stress of managing children's education from home. This period of crisis has illustrated the critical need for adaptive coping strategies and robust support systems for parents navigating these multifaceted stressors.

Given the complex nature of parental anxiety and its impact on families, creating a detailed tool to measure this anxiety is essential. This is not just to spot and gauge anxiety levels but also to guide specific help where it's needed.

Research Questions

The study sought to identify the reliability and validity of the newly developed anxiety inventory in assessing anxiety among parents. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of reliability of the anxiety inventory in measuring the anxiety manifestations of parents in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive,
 - 1.2. emotional,
 - 1.3. behavioral, and
 - 1.4. physiological?
2. What recommendations may be forwarded for the improvement of the mental health of parents particularly in handling anxiety?

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The participants of this study were the parents of the enrolled students at the two HEIs of Cebu City. They consist of 192 males (27.54%) and 505 females (72.46%) with a mean age of 41.19. It was conducted on the day the respective institutions held a parents' workshop on mental health. The workshop was facilitated by a Registered Psychologist and was assisted by guidance counselors, principals, teachers, psychometricians, and psychology interns.

Procedure

The HEIs where the study was conducted, respectively, had workshops about mental health for their institutions. They were held on different dates. During the registration and ushering of the participants, the tool and instructions were given to them. They were informed of the option of wanting to answer the survey or not.

Guidance counselors, teachers, and psychology student interns were strategically assigned within the venue to assist the participants with their concerns or clarifications.

The researcher then prepared the inventory to identify the level of stress of the research participants. An informed consent form was stated at the bottom page of the instrument for the research participants to sign should they agree to participate in the research conducted. An appointment was set with the guidance counselors of the two participating HEIs of Cebu City. The questionnaires were given to each department for review and reproduction.

Before the start of the workshop, a one-hour ushering-in activity was done, where participants were given the instruments and instructions. Guidance counselors, teachers, and psychology interns were strategically situated in the venue to assist at least 5-7 parents, making sure that someone would answer their questions or clarifications. Once the questionnaires were given to them, the consent forms were cut off and gathered, but they were placed separately to further keep the answers random and confidential.

All the questionnaires were then collated into one population. Each statement of the inventory and its corresponding answers were then tallied to produce their frequency and percentage in the population. The researcher then clustered the statements into tables that showed similarities in nature and labeled it with its respective theme.

Instrument

The Anxiety Inventory is a self-report tool used to gauge levels of anxiety of parents. A 4-point anchored scale is used to rate the frequency of each manifestation within a fourteen-day timeframe with 0 for Not at all, 1 for Less than half of the number of days in 2 weeks (1-6 days), 2 for More than half of the number of days in 2 weeks (7-13 days), and 3 for Always (Everyday). These constructs assessed various manifestations such as cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological.

Scoring

Each statement in the inventory is scored based on how strongly the manifestations were felt during a specific period. A score of 0 indicates that the manifestations were not felt at all, while a score of 3 indicates that they were felt every day. Total scores were summed up to get the mean score and were classified as either No, Low, Moderate, and High.

Content Validity of the Instrument

In the development of the inventory, the crucial role of content validity was highlighted, emphasizing its necessity for tests to comprehensively cover the constructs they are designed to assess. This entails a detailed verification process, often requiring consensus among experts for thorough evaluation (Nikolopoulou, 2023). To ensure the assessment tool's relevance, clarity, and comprehensive coverage of the intended construct, an initial review of the items was conducted by experts in psychology, parenting, and psychometrics. Moreover, the qualitative phase of the study utilized a content analysis approach, incorporating semi-structured, in-depth interviews with three psychologists and two psychometrists, all with significant experience in working with parents within their psychological practice. This expert feedback proved instrumental in refining the inventory, guiding the revision, addition, and deletion of items to enhance the instrument's content validity. Such a process was pivotal in ensuring that the inventory accurately reflects the domain of anxiety among parents, thus making it a valid tool for assessing this specific psychological construct.

Pilot Testing

To ensure the questionnaire really captures what it's meant to, we tested a first version with a small group of 10 parents, split evenly between men and women. This test helped us see if the questions were clear and if the questionnaire was easy to use.

Data Treatment

To evaluate the internal consistency or reliability of the questionnaire items, Cronbach's alpha was employed. This method involves assessing the shared variance or covariance among the items within the instrument compared to the total variance observed. The underlying principle is that a higher covariance among the items, relative to the overall variance, signifies a reliable instrument. Essentially, Cronbach's alpha calculates the average of all possible split-half reliabilities, providing a standardized measure of agreement between the items on a scale from 0 to 1. Higher Cronbach's alpha values suggest a higher level of agreement among the items, reflecting consistency in participants' responses across a set of questions. This consistency is crucial for the development and evaluation of new survey instruments. A Cronbach's alpha threshold of 0.7 was established as a benchmark for sufficient consistency, indicating that the measure is reliable. While values around 0.7 are considered minimally acceptable, they are not ideal; conversely, excessively high values may suggest redundancy among the questions.

RESULTS

In order to assess the reliability of the statements in the inventory, it applied Cronbach's alpha as a key metric, which is still used in present studies (Amirrudin et al., 2020). This was used as it has been seen as a fundamental tool to evaluate internal consistency or reliability of the measurement scale employed within the research framework (Goforth, 2015). It aimed to gauge the interrelatedness of the items, showing its consistency to measure the expected construct.

Anxiety Inventory

**Table 1.1 Cognitive Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics
(Cronbach Alpha)**

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.928
95% CI lower bound	0.920
95% CI upper bound	0.936

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
A2	0.921
A3	0.922
A14	0.919
A15	0.917
A16	0.919
A22	0.923
A23	0.924
A25	0.919
A35	0.922
A31	0.924

Table 1.1 presents reliability statistics obtained through a frequentist analysis, evaluating both the overall scale and individual items within the assessment. The scale's reliability, assessed via Cronbach's α , demonstrates a notably high level of internal consistency with a point estimate of 0.928, categorized as 'Excellent.' This score indicates that collectively, the items within the scale show exceptional consistency in measuring the construct under study. Moreover, the 95% confidence interval for the scale's reliability, ranging from 0.920 to 0.936, further supports this high level of consistency. Additionally, the individual item reliability statistics illustrate Cronbach's α values if each respective item were to be omitted from the scale. These values, which consistently range from 0.917 to 0.924, show that the scale's overall reliability remains unaffected when any one item is removed, supporting the assessment's stability and consistency in gauging parents' anxiety levels through cognitive manifestations. Sample statements of this instrument to check on the cognitive manifestations of parents' anxieties show a wide range of symptoms, including Statement 15 "unable to control my worries", Statement 22

“experiencing flashbacks of undesirable experiences”, and Statement 25 “not seeing myself as capable as other people”. These statements were considered as these manifestations were also seen in existing literature, just like those of Alzawad et al. (2019), Karatzias et al., (2016), Aldao and Nolen-Hoeksema (2012), and Gloster et al. (2014).

Table 1.2 Emotional Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.924
95% CI lower bound	0.915
95% CI upper bound	0.932

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
A6	0.918
A10	0.916
A18	0.915
A24	0.916
A28	0.919
A29	0.914
A30	0.911
A33	0.914
A36	0.915

Table 1.2 presents the reliability statistics from a frequentist analysis that highlight the assessment tool's individual items as well as its overall scale. With a Cronbach's α of 0.924, which is considered "Excellent," the reliability of the scale is assessed, demonstrating a strong degree of internal consistency. This score is indicative of a reliable and strong measure of the construct under evaluation, with strong coherence among the scale's items. Furthermore, the reliability of the scale's 95% confidence interval (CI) spans from 0.915 to 0.932, supporting the high degree of consistency seen in the measurements. Furthermore, the Cronbach's α values for each individual item's reliability statistics are displayed if that item were hypothetically removed from the scale. The values exhibit a consistent range of 0.911 to 0.919, indicating that the removal of a single item from the scale would not substantially impair the overall reliability. This further

validates the assessment's stability and reliability in assessing the emotional manifestations of anxiety experienced by the parents. In order to check the emotional manifestations of parents, manifestations indicated in other literature were considered, such as those indicated by the National Institute of Mental Health (2022) and by Wong and Rapee (2016). Some statements in the instrument included Statement 18 "fearful of being judged", Statement 30 "feeling constantly worried and afraid about what might happen", and Statement 33 "fearful of becoming a burden to other people".

Table 1.3 Behavioral Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.865
95% CI lower bound	0.850
95% CI upper bound	0.879

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
A1	0.848
A4	0.850
A8	0.845
A9	0.844
A17	0.846
A19	0.867
A21	0.851
A27	0.848
A32	0.855

Table 1.3 shows the significant reliability data from a frequentist analysis which evaluates the tool's individual items as well as the entire scale with an emphasis on behavioral manifestations. The reliability of the scale, as determined by Cronbach's α , demonstrates a strong degree of internal consistency, with a point estimate of 0.865, denoting 'Good.' This score suggests that, collectively, the items in the scale demonstrate a commendable consistency in measuring behavioral manifestations, although there might be slight variations among them. Furthermore, the 95% confidence interval (CI) for the scale's reliability ranges between 0.850 and 0.879, supporting the observed level of consistency within the measurements. In the same context, the individual item reliability statistics display the Cronbach's α values if each respective item were hypothetically

excluded from the scale. These values range between 0.844 and 0.867, demonstrating that removing any single item would not drastically affect the overall reliability, indicating a stable and reliable assessment tool in comprehensively evaluating behavioral manifestations among parents. Sample statements for the behavioral manifestations included Statement 1 “becoming restless”, Statement 27 “avoids conversing with people”, and Statement 32 “cannot look at people in the eyes”. These statements were just some of the manifestations that even current literature has observed, such as Craske et al.’s (2017) and Howell et al.’s (2015), furthering its relevance in the instrument.

Table 1.4 Physiological Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.895
95% CI lower bound	0.882
95% CI upper bound	0.906

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
A5	0.883
A7	0.888
A11	0.875
A12	0.874
A13	0.882
A20	0.891
A26	0.880
A34	0.879

Table 1.4 shows how reliable the inventory is for measuring physiological manifestations of anxiety. The Cronbach's α is 0.895, which is considered 'Good.' This means the tool does a good job of measuring physiological manifestations overall. The numbers between 0.882 and 0.906 tell us the likely range of how consistent the results are. The individual item reliability statistics portray Cronbach's α values if each respective item were hypothetically removed from the scale. These values vary between 0.874 and 0.891, demonstrating that removing any single item would not significantly compromise the overall reliability, reinforcing the stability and reliability of the assessment in comprehensively evaluating physiological manifestations of anxiety among parents.

Some statements included Statement 5 “experienced hot and/or cold sweats”, Statement 13 “have shortness of breath or chest pain”, and Statement 20 “feeling numb or tingling sensation in some parts of the body” to check on parents’ physiological manifestations of anxiety. The consideration of such were due to them being evident even in other literature, such as Barrera-Valencia et al. (2020) and Folk (2022).

DISCUSSION

The reliability statistics from the frequentist analysis provide a robust framework for evaluating the internal consistency of the newly developed inventory designed to assess parental anxiety across cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological manifestations. The findings across Tables 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and 1.4 collectively highlight the instrument's strong reliability and the coherent structure of its scale, reinforcing its effectiveness in capturing the multifaceted nature of parental anxiety.

Table 1.1 illustrates an 'Excellent' level of internal consistency in measuring cognitive manifestations of anxiety, with a Cronbach's α of 0.928. This high degree of reliability is further supported by a narrow confidence interval, suggesting that the scale items are exceptionally consistent in assessing cognitive aspects of parental anxiety. The analysis also demonstrates the scale's stability; removing any single item does not significantly impact its overall reliability.

Similarly, Table 1.2, focusing on emotional manifestations, reports a Cronbach's α of 0.924, also classified as 'Excellent.' This indicates a high level of agreement among items measuring emotional aspects of anxiety, with a confidence interval reinforcing this consistency. The minor changes in reliability upon the hypothetical removal of individual items further validate the scale's robustness in evaluating emotional manifestations.

The analysis presented in Table 1.3 shifts the focus to behavioral manifestations, reporting a 'Good' Cronbach's α of 0.865. Despite a slight decrease compared to the cognitive and emotional aspects, this still represents a commendable level of internal consistency, affirming the scale's efficacy in capturing behavioral expressions of anxiety. The confidence interval and minimal impact of item removal on reliability underscore the tool's comprehensive approach to assessing behavioral aspects.

Finally, Table 1.4 addresses physiological manifestations with a Cronbach's α of 0.895, deemed 'Good.' This highlights the tool's ability to consistently measure physiological responses associated with anxiety, supported by a tight confidence interval. The stability of the scale is again evident, as the removal of individual items does not significantly affect the reliability.

Collectively, these results affirm the inventory's capability to provide a multidimensional assessment of parental anxiety with high reliability. The consistent

findings across different manifestations of anxiety underscore the importance of a nuanced approach to understanding and measuring this complex condition. This thorough evaluation of the tool's internal consistency is pivotal in ensuring its applicability in both clinical and research settings, aiming to facilitate targeted interventions and promote the well-being of families affected by parental anxiety.

Conclusions

This research confirms that the detailed inventory for assessing parental anxiety is reliable, effectively measuring anxiety through cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological signs. It shows high accuracy in understanding different aspects of anxiety, with strong consistency in its results, even when individual items are removed. This means the tool is well-designed and stable. Its thorough approach helps grasp the complex issue of parental anxiety clearly, making it valuable for both clinical use and research. Importantly, this inventory can lead to specific actions that help improve the well-being of families, underlining its importance in tackling the challenges parental anxiety brings and in supporting the development of healthier family environments and outcomes for children.

Recommendations

The findings from the reliability analysis of the inventory designed to assess parental anxiety across cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological dimensions offer several avenues for future research and application. Here are some recommendations based on these results:

1. **Further Validation in Diverse Populations:** Given the high level of internal consistency across various dimensions of parental anxiety, future research should aim to validate this inventory in diverse populations. This includes parents from different cultural backgrounds, socioeconomic statuses, and family structures to ensure the tool's applicability and reliability across a broad spectrum of individuals.
2. **Longitudinal Studies:** Conduct longitudinal studies to assess how parental anxiety changes over time and in response to different life events or interventions. This will help in understanding the temporal stability of the inventory and the dynamic nature of parental anxiety.
3. **Comparison with Clinical Diagnoses:** Compare the inventory's assessments with clinical diagnoses of anxiety to evaluate its diagnostic accuracy. This could involve correlating the scores from the inventory with diagnoses made through clinical interviews or other standardized diagnostic tools for anxiety.
4. **Integration into Intervention Programs:** Use the inventory as a pre- and post-assessment tool in intervention programs aimed at reducing parental anxiety. This can help in quantifying the effectiveness of various therapeutic approaches and programs designed to support parents dealing with anxiety.

5. **Exploration of Subscale Interactions:** Investigate the interactions between the cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological dimensions of parental anxiety. This could lead to a deeper understanding of how different aspects of anxiety are interrelated and impact parental behavior and child outcomes.
6. **Development of Tailored Interventions:** Based on the inventory's findings, develop targeted interventions that address specific manifestations of anxiety. For example, if a parent scores particularly high on physiological symptoms, interventions could focus on stress reduction techniques and physical wellness.
7. **Education and Awareness Programs:** Utilize the inventory in educational settings and awareness programs to help parents recognize signs of anxiety in themselves. This could be coupled with resources and guidance on seeking professional help and employing self-help strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All applicable institutional guidelines where the study was conducted were followed. The participants were informed of their freedom to answer the survey instrument. All who had submitted their answers had written informed consent.

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